

Frequency-Domain Benchmark of the Reactivity-Insertion Transient in the Molten-Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE)

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ABSTRACT

Benchmarking molten-salt reactors (MSRs) is needed given their prospective deployment and inherent complexity. A reactivity-insertion transient is simulated for the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) using a tightly coupled model that integrates neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, and delayed-neutron precursor advection/decay. The workflow leverages Serpent's capabilities to generate cross-sections, which are later incorporated within GeN-Foam, a multiphysics tool that simulates power transients during reactivity insertion. The model showed a good agreement with the MSRE response in the frequency domain (gain/phase trends across the experimentally tested band). The model captured the measured attenuation and phase lead introduced by fuel and graphite temperature feedbacks. The agreement in the results indicates that the model accurately represents the underlying MSRE dynamics. Analysis showed low-pass behavior for both feedback components (fuel and graphite) at two different roll-off frequencies, and the destructive effect of fuel recirculation on the power gain at the loop residence time frequency. This work provides a high-fidelity model that explains MSRE behavior with validation in both time and frequency domains.

Keywords: molten-salt reactor; MSRE; reactivity-insertion transient; frequency response; multi-physics

1. INTRODUCTION

Benchmarks are essential as a reference case to validate model performances on existing experimental data, guiding future reactor designs. The Molten-Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) offers a uniquely rich dataset for this purpose. When operated on Uranium-233, the MSRE exhibited distinctive dynamics: a lower delayed-neutron fraction compared to Uranium-235, transport (drift) of precursors in the circulating fuel, and multiple temperature-feedback paths involving the fuel salt, graphite moderator, and external loop. Together, these features make the MSRE an especially complex system for modeling.

To capture this complexity, we developed a multiphysics benchmark for the MSRE reactivity-insertion transient. The model treats the tight coupling between neutronics and thermal hydraulics and explicitly tracks spatially dependent quantities—including precursor transport. In doing so, it aims to reproduce the MSRE's experimental behavior.

A model comparison is performed against MSRE reactivity-insertion data in the frequency domains. The time series experiment of the power transient contains a significant measurement noise because of gas bubbles entrained into the primary loop, which limits the judgment of the model performance in predicting the experiment.

The experimental frequency-domain data provide a clearer, low-noise basis for validation. The MSRE exhibits a predominantly low-pass response: slow reactivity perturbations (smaller than the roll-off frequency of the core) are strongly attenuated and accrue substantial phase lag, while fast reactivity perturbations (larger than the roll-off frequency of the core) get little attenuation and small phase lag.

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2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Geometry and model layout

Figure 1 shows the benchmark model used for the MSRE reactivity-insertion transient. The transient is interpreted as a sequence of events from which we extract the key fields (velocity, temperature, power/flux, and precursor concentrations) governed by coupled conservation laws. Since these fields vary in space and time, the vessel region is modeled as an axisymmetric slice to capture radial symmetry, while the external piping is treated with volume-averaged (lumped) fields where detailed spatial variation is not essential; nevertheless, the residence time is conserved within each cell zone.

Figure 1. The mesh and cell zones of the MSRE model.

2.2. Multiphysics Workflow

Reactivity-insertion transients require tight coupling between reactor physics and thermal-hydraulics because temperature changes drive reactivity changes. We therefore adopt a multiphysics workflow (Figure 2) that progressively develops the case needed to run the transient. Macroscopic cross sections are generated in Serpent-2.2.1 [1] using the MSRE benchmark Serpent model [2], the benchmark used endf7 for both microscopic cross section and thermal scattering thermal scattering libraries, the the fuel composition updated from U-235 to the U-233 fresh fuel salt [3]. These cross sections are supplied to GeN-Foam(v2206), a multiphysics framework featuring a diffusion neutronics solver coupled to a porous media thermal-hydraulic solver [4] to establish a steady state. That steady state provides the reference condition for a point-kinetics (PK) [5] solver used to simulate the transients. The time step for the steady-state simulations is determined by the most restrictive condition between a Courant-number constraint and a user-prescribed maximum allowable relative power variation (set to 0.02 in this study) [6]. For transient, the Nyquist stability criterion is employed as the basis for selecting the time step.

2.3. Thermal-hydraulic solver

This section details the implementation of the thermal-hydraulic model of the MSRE in GeN-Foam. The primary and secondary loop models are calibrated such that core and loop residence times match

Figure 2. Schematic of the workflow for the multiphysics case.

MSRE operating conditions of ~ 25 s full recirculation time. This preserves the advective transport and recirculation delays that control feedback phasing and amplitude. Regarding the thermophysical properties, see Table I which shows the all the values evaluated at 911 K. For the heat-transfer coefficients, two interfaces are treated explicitly:

1. **Fuel channels (core):** A core average Nusselt (Nu) has been adopted for the convective heat-transfer coefficients from [7]. This Nu number resulted in a heat transfer coefficient of $317.48 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$.
2. **Heat exchanger:** The overall heat-transfer coefficient $3406.8 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is set from the post-modification experimental characterization of the MSRE heat exchanger [8]. Because the secondary coolant salt has thermophysical properties similar to the primary, and due to current software limitations, the same property set is applied on both sides of the exchanger.

Table I. Thermophysical properties of the fuel salt.

Category	Property	Symbol	Value (SI)
Equation of state	Density	ρ	2247.8 kg m^{-3}
Thermodynamics	Specific heat	C_p	$1967.8 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Transport	Dynamic viscosity	μ	0.01 Pa s
Transport	Prandtl number	Pr	21.5

2.4. Reactor Physics

For the diffusion solver, macroscopic two-groups cross sections for fresh U-233 fuel salt [3] are generated with Serpent using the MSRE benchmark model [2]. Two isothermal cross-sectional datasets are generated at 911 K to 1000 K for GeN-Foam, allowing square-root-based interpolation between them during steady-state calculations.

After the study state is achieved, it is taken as the reference conditions for the point-kinetics (PK) model [5]. During transient the PK solver uses a modified point kinetic equation where the spatial tracking of the precursors is considered and weighted by the total flux distribution, the same weighting is applied on the temperature distribution to compute the temperature feedback on reactivity. For the full derivation of the equations please see [5].

2.4.1. Temperature-feedback coefficients

The temperature-feedback coefficients are taken from zero-power experimental measurements [9]. Engel reports multiple isothermal temperature coefficients corresponding to different estimated void fractions. In this work, the coefficient associated with the nominal pump speed (≈ 1180 RPM) is selected to match the conditions of the dynamic analysis experiments [10]. The measured isothermal coefficient at 1180 RPM is -13.3 pcm/K. The graphite temperature coefficient is taken as -5.7 pcm/K, consistent with the MSRE estimates and the Serpent-based evaluation (0.144 pcm/K difference). The fuel temperature coefficient is then defined by difference as

$$\alpha_f \equiv \alpha_{\text{iso}} - \alpha_g = -13.3 - (-5.7) = -7.6 \text{ pcm/K.}$$

This -7.6 pcm/K value is used as the fuel temperature feedback coefficient in the GeN-Foam PK solver. A key limitation is that the fuel temperature coefficient is not independently computed from first principles (e.g., via temperature-dependent cross sections combined with an explicit void model), but inferred from the zero-power isothermal measurement after subtracting the graphite contribution. Importantly, the MSRE team explicitly attributes the reduced magnitude of the temperature coefficient under circulation to gas-bubble entrainment: they note “an appreciable amount of entrained cover gas circulating with the salt” and explain that the associated temperature-dependent void fraction offsets the salt density effect, thereby “reducing the magnitude of the reactivity effect of slowly varying temperature” [9]. This interpretation is reinforced by their subsequent repeat measurement at reduced pump speed, where the loop bubble fraction was observed to be very low and “practically no bubbles” circulated with the salt, yielding a higher (more negative) temperature coefficient [9]. However, for the U-233 campaigns, direct measurements of void variation with temperature are not available, preventing a quantitative separation of Doppler, thermal expansion of the salt and void contributions.

2.5. Reactor Dynamics and Feedback Structure

Figure 3. Equivalent block diagram of the MSRE system adopted from [11].

The MSRE dynamics can be represented by The block diagram in Figure 3 with a forward (open-loop) path $G_0(\omega)$, a feedback path $H(j\omega)$, and the closed-loop response:

$$G_{cl}(j\omega) = \frac{G_0(j\omega)}{1 + L(j\omega)} \tag{1}$$

$$L(j\omega) = G_0(j\omega) H(j\omega) \tag{2}$$

The forward (open-loop) path $G_0(j\omega)$ maps input reactivity $\Delta\rho_{in}$ to power N without temperature feedback. In terms of point-kinetics, the power rise is governed by the prompt generation time Λ and the delayed-neutron groups with decay constants λ_i (time constants $\tau_i \equiv 1/\lambda_i$) and fractions β_i .

The feedback block represents temperature-driven reactivity: power surge introduces thermal responses in the fuel and graphite, producing temperature changes that are weighted by the (negative) reactivity coefficients α_f and α_g . Writing the temperature paths explicitly,

$$H(j\omega) = \alpha_f G_{N \rightarrow T_f}(j\omega) + \alpha_g G_{N \rightarrow T_g}(j\omega), \quad (3)$$

where $G_{N \rightarrow T_f}$ and $G_{N \rightarrow T_g}$ map power to fuel and graphite temperatures, respectively.

3. RESULTS

For validation, the experimental time-domain traces are relatively noisy, which limits quantitative assessment of model validity, but they still capture the expected sequence of reactor behavior. By contrast, the experimental frequency-domain data provide a clearer, lower-noise basis for validation and are extensively leveraged in this work. The reason behind the lower noise in the frequency response data is that consistent, periodic reactivity signal is reinforced overtime which helps eliminating the random bubbles noise.

Figure 4. Bode plot of the flux at 5 MW power.

In the frequency domain, Figure 4 shows the open-loop response (no feedback) and the closed-loop response (with temperature feedback). The case integrating temperature feedback (close-loop) has a magnitude strongly attenuated at low frequency and approaches the no-feedback magnitude at high frequency, while the phase shows additional lag from thermal transport. This trend reflects finite thermal time constants (τ_f and τ_g): feedback is effective for slow perturbations and progressively less effective as the perturbation rate increases. The open-loop simulation represents the forward path $G_0(j\omega)$

from input reactivity $\Delta\rho_{in}$ to the output power, without temperature feedback (zero-power baseline). Its gain decreases with increasing frequency because the delayed-neutron contribution is progressively attenuated as ω exceeds the dominant precursor decay constants λ_i ; the response tends toward the prompt/transport limit with increasing phase lag. By contrast, the closed-loop response at high power (5 MW) in Figure 4 is:

$$G_{cl}(j\omega) = \frac{G_0(j\omega)}{1 + L(j\omega)} \quad (1)$$

$$L(j\omega) = \alpha_f \frac{\Delta T_f(j\omega)}{\Delta\rho_{in}} + \alpha_g \frac{\Delta T_g(j\omega)}{\Delta\rho_{in}} \quad (5)$$

so the temperature feedback reshapes G_0 —lowering gain and advancing phase—consistent with the negative temperature coefficients $\alpha_f, \alpha_g < 0$.

Figure 5. Bode plot of the fuel and graphite temperature at 5 MW power.

The individual contribution of the fuel and graphite to the temperature feedback can be highlighted by representing the temperature gain, exhibited in Figure 5. It shows that both fuel and graphite temperature paths behave as low-pass elements: flat gain and near-zero phase at low frequency, then roll-off past their corner frequencies. In the results, the graphite corner precedes the fuel corner ($\omega_g < \omega_f$), so the graphite attenuates earlier. This earlier roll-off is attributable to a longer effective thermal path (fuel→graphite), i.e., a larger τ_g than the effective in-fuel time constant τ_f . Around $\omega \approx \omega_g$, the fuel path exhibits a slight gain bump because reduced heat transfer to graphite keeps more energy in the fuel; nevertheless, the net feedback $|L|$ decreases there as the graphite phase shrinks. Beyond ω_f , the fuel path also rolls off, and both thermal contributions are weak.

Near $\omega \approx 0.25$ rad/s (period ≈ 25 s, which is the loop residence time), the transport delay can align constructively with in-core heating, producing a local bump in the fuel temperature gain; at nearby frequencies it can be destructive, producing a dip. At sufficiently high frequency ($\omega_g < \omega_f \ll \omega$), both fuel and graphite lose temperature gain, and the closed-loop magnitude and phase approach the open-loop values, indicating minimal feedback.

The largest mismatch between measurement and simulation results occurs at high frequency (0.2 rad s^{-1} to 0.8 rad s^{-1}) Table II, where the experimental gain is lower and the phase, more lagging than the model. MSRE reports note that rod-tip motion likely does not reproduce the high-frequency component of the commanded drive (rod flexibility) [10] and that equipment limitations (amplitude bias, deadband) affected the input signal- effects that attenuate the injected reactivity and add effective lag at high- ω [12]. In the mid-band (0.04 rad s^{-1} to 0.1 rad s^{-1}), the remaining phase offset is consistent with using a first-order, lumped heat-transfer model for the fuel and graphite. This reduces the graphite path to a single pole, making its roll-off too shallow and too late; graphite retains gain longer, so the fuel-temperature gain climbs too slowly. A higher-order model that includes interfacial exchange and internal diffusion/conduction in the graphite should steepen and advance the graphite roll-off, causing the fuel-temperature gain to rise faster and reducing the mid-band mismatch

Table II. Power Bode error by frequency band (model vs. experiment).

Band (rad s ⁻¹)	Gain MAPE (%)	Gain RMSE [dB]	Phase RMSE [°]
Low (≤ 0.05 , $N=5$)	6.88	0.84	7.99
Mid ($0.05\text{--}0.2$, $N=15$)	4.48	0.46	3.02
High (> 0.2 , $N=32$)	7.40	0.72	15.19

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{100\%}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \left| \frac{y_k - \hat{y}_k}{y_k} \right|, \text{ RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (y_k - \hat{y}_k)^2}, \text{ where } N \text{ is the number of test frequencies in the band. For Gain MAPE, } y_k, \hat{y}_k \text{ are linear magnitudes; for Gain RMSE, } (y_k, \hat{y}_k) \text{ are magnitudes in dB; for Phase RMSE, phases are in degrees.}$$

4. CONCLUSIONS

We benchmarked the MSRE reactivity–insertion transient using a coupled neutronics/thermal–hydraulics model that tracks delayed–neutron precursor drift. The model reproduces the prompt 5 MW to 5.7 MW rise and the higher post–transient steady state. In the frequency domain, power–gain mismatch is small (RMSE ≈ 0.56 dB; MAPE $\approx 5.8\%$), while phase agreement is good at low–mid frequencies but degrades at high ω . These results suggest that resolving fuel–graphite heat transfer will reduce the mismatch to the experimental data at the mid-band, and for the residual high–frequency phase deficit tied to the equipment limitation during the experiment that made inaccurate data at high frequency .

In summery this work demonstrates the continuous effort in code benchmarking for the MSRE reactor type, leveraging the available MSRE data. This paper investigates both the time and frequency domains' reactor response to a reactivity insertion transient. The model shows an overall good agreement, capturing the temporal power evolution and the frequency gain and phase reported in the MSRE data. The use of the experimental frequency response for validation provides a better judgment on the model's agreement with the experiment. In the futhure more trasient will be benchmarked using the same framework presented in this work such as pump transients and natural circulation in the primary loop.

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